

1 **Identification of a therapeutic target in kidney disease.**

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8 We study morbidity and mortality in humans. Among the ten leading causes of death in the developed world include chronic kidney disease. We used whole transcriptome discovery methods to identify novel therapeutic targets in kidney disease. We report here the identification of Eda2r as a leading candidate therapeutic target in chronic kidney disease in humans.

9 Citations

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